

Memo ODISSEI Portal Development In Macroscopic

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Introduction

This memo is written to give an overview of the general direction DANS would like to take with the ODISSEI Portal developments within the Macroscope project. This document provides an overview of the status of the ODISSEI Portal as well as the direction of development that is envisioned to ensure the Portal is a sustainable and resilient service for the Dutch social sciences community. This document should be seen as a guiding document that can be used to further specify the plans, division of work and distribution of hours within the project.

Background

The ODISSEI Portal is the result of work that was done within the ODISSEI roadmap project, executed from 2020 to 2024 (NWO grant number 184.035.014). ODISSEI (Open Data Infrastructure for Social Science and Economic Innovations) is the national research infrastructure for the Dutch social sciences, and the roadmap project was received to strengthen the infrastructure.

The ODISSEI Portal was created to be a discovery service for social sciences datasets from different data providers in the Netherlands. The Portal is part of a larger infrastructure ODISSEI has started to build which simplifies finding, accessing, and reusing social sciences data and provides corresponding services through one integrated interface. The Portal is one element in this infrastructure focusing on the [findability](#) of datasets and is linked to the Data Access Broker (DAB) which aims to broker [access](#) to data and the Knowledge Graph (KG) which connects data and other research objects.

Note that when we refer to the “ODISSEI Portal” in this document, we mean the metadata aggregation and discovery service that is available at <https://portal.odissei.nl/>. In other contexts, such as earlier project descriptions, “ODISSEI Portal” has been used to describe the collection of services that relate to finding and accessing data which includes the metadata aggregation and discovery service, but also the DAB and KG. Since these elements are separate services, developed by different organizations, we prefer to describe them separately, and limit the term “ODISSEI Portal” to the metadata aggregation and discovery service that is developed by DANS.

DANS has been responsible for building and maintaining the Portal since the start of the roadmap project in 2020. We have chosen to work with [Dataverse software](#) to reuse knowledge and components available for the DANS Data Stations and DataverseNL. The ODISSEI Portal, however, fulfills a different function than the Data Station SSH, focusing on data discovery across Dutch data providers, as was outlined in [this memo](#).

At the end of the roadmap project (December 2024), a production version of the Portal was released which was presented at the ODISSEI conference as well as through [a dedicated webinar](#). Notably, as part of the project agreements, DANS has committed itself to maintaining the Portal for a minimum of five years after the end of the roadmap project (i.e., until the end of 2029).

In 2025, the Portal was [maintained and updates were implemented](#) as part of the work of the FAIR workstream of the [SSHOC-NL project](#) (NWO grant number 184.036.020). SSHOC-NL is a project in which ODISSEI and CLARIAH (Common Lab Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities) collaborate to develop a state-of-the-art infrastructure for social science and humanities (SSH) research, connecting services and aligning infrastructure that ODISSEI and CLARIAH have been investing in.

[In the SSHOC-NL deliverable “Overview of Existing Data Discovery Mechanisms and Future Directions for \(Common\) Search”](#), the latest features of the Portal are described and placed it in the context of data discovery solutions for SSH data within the Netherlands, including INEO, a discovery portal developed for the humanities by CLARIAH.

New Project: Macroscope

From February 2026 onwards, the Portal is further maintained and developed as part of the [Macroscope project](#) (NWO grant number 184.037.001) with a dedicated task.

Macroscope aims to further mature the available SSH infrastructure components with the overarching goal to allow connecting available datasets, tools, and workflows to study large and complex societal research questions. Macroscope is closely related to SSHOC-NL with a large overlap in the partners, and both projects will run simultaneously for the next couple of years.

Within Macroscope, the Portal is part of Task 1.1 Subtask 2 *Metadata portal and data discovery*. DANS is task lead for this task which also contains work on the Data Access Broker (DAB, managed by SURF), the data discovery platform INEO from CLARIAH (managed by HuC) and the Knowledge Graph (KG, managed by VU). Note that while DANS is leading task 1.1, DANS itself is only responsible for delivering the Portal service, while the other services are developed by the other mentioned partners.

ODISSEI Portal - Plan of Work

DANS' plan for the ODISSEI Portal service can broadly be divided into three aspects:

- We want to **maintain** a solid, resilient infrastructure for the Portal.
- We want to **grow** the number of providers included, as well as the Portal's reach.

- We plan to **innovate** functionalities to make the service sustainable and improve the search and user interface.

We outline these three strands of work below and then discuss the Portal in the context of the larger infrastructure available in the Dutch SSH network and how we plan to integrate the Portal further with the DAB and KG, as well as align with sister services like CLARIAH's INEO.

Maintain

With maintenance, we refer to activities that ensure the Portal remains a functional and up-to-date service that is relevant to the SSH community.

This includes ensuring the Portal's software is functional, and any issues or bugs are addressed in a timely manner. We also include regular updates and upgrades, editing documentation, and providing support for existing metadata providers under the definition of maintenance.

Re-design for resilience and sustainability

One important task in Macroscopic will be to scan the current implementation of the Portal for improvements. The current architecture is quite complex and fragmented comprising different elements that were developed over the course of the previous project(s). Assessing how we can make the service architecture more simple and solid will be crucial to ensure the service is resilient and can be sustained in the future while keeping maintenance costs as low as possible.

Grow

With the solid basis established in the first part of our work, we want to expand the Portal to include more data providers ensuring we cover data from all ODISSEI members. In this work, we also plan to connect the Portal to European data discovery platforms, starting with CESSDA. Lastly, engaging with users is also an aspect of the work to grow the Portal. This includes promoting the Portal as well as working with the stakeholders to discuss Portal functionalities and align expectations around the service.

Onboarding new data providers

The Portal already contains metadata from major data providers in the Netherlands and from many ODISSEI member organizations, but an ongoing task is to engage with data providers not yet onboarded. This can include universities which are ODISSEI members that operate repositories outside of DataverseNL, but may also include international surveys that collect data in the Netherlands which are interesting for the community. Ensuring the Portal covers relevant datasets is essential to ensure the Portal is used and relevant for the community. We already provide guidance for new data providers and

have a set of [requirements](#) that providers need to comply with. These requirements and documentation form the basis for discussions with potential providers.

Connecting the Portal to European infrastructures

A longstanding wish for the Portal is to ensure that the metadata that is collected is findable in European discovery platforms. An important catalogue is the CESSDA Data Catalogue (CDC) which collects and harmonizes social sciences metadata from CESSDA providers and makes them available in the EOSC landscape. Discussions with CESSDA to onboard the Portal into the CDC have started in 2025 within SSHOC-NL and a letter of support has been sent by ODISSEI and DANS to the CESSDA Main Office asking for permission to further assess the integration. Space to take this further has been allocated in the SSHOC-NL project for 2026 and will transfer to Macroscopic in the following period.

The goal of "connecting" the ODISSEI Portal to European infrastructures, also requires improving its interoperability, with other data catalogs and infrastructures. One solution that is gaining popularity is the metadata application profile, DCAT-AP. [DCAT-AP 3.0](#) is an application profile for metadata, which provides a minimal common basis within Europe to **share Datasets and Data Services cross-border and cross-domain**. DCAT-AP is developed by [Semantic Interoperability Community \(SEMIC\)](#), whose goals are to provide common standards, specifications, and a community platform for European public administrations to exchange data more seamlessly. Within the context of SSHOC-NL, in 2026 DANS will be working on deliverable 2026-D06, which will focus on the development of a DCAT-AP metadata exporter for Dataverse. Once development is complete, it will require a minimal effort to enable the exporter within the Portal.

Promoting the Portal

Despite the Portal being available for several years already, the visibility of the Portal can be improved and within Macroscopic we want to showcase the Portal to more users to ensure awareness of the Portal increases. Especially when we can implement improvements to the interface and user search experience (see next paragraph), it will be valuable to ensure these innovations are shared widely with the SSH community.

Innovate

An important aspect of the work in Macroscopic will be the innovation of the Portal. A long list of wishes for improvement exists which will be reevaluated at the start of the project. A key aspect of the innovation effort will be to keep **sustainability** in mind. As mentioned above, the current architecture of the Portal is quite complex and fragmented already, and efforts to innovate will focus on simplifying the architecture and building a **resilient** service.

We envision that the innovation of the service will focus on two aspects: Improving the User interface and improving the dataset search capabilities.

User Interface

The user interface is currently based on standard features of Dataverse. As Dataverse is a software focused on repositories (that hold data and metadata), rather than on metadata catalogs (that hold metadata exclusively), the interface contains several elements that users find confusing. This includes, for instance, the log-in option and the download statistics.

The ability to customize the interface is also limited with the current implementation of Dataverse. This leads to a similar look and feel between the Portal, the Data Stations, and DataverseNL. While these services fulfill distinct functions, the similarity in the design has been confusing to users, which makes a more custom interface an urgent need.

A promising development that could solve the issues listed above is the announcement that Harvard, the lead developing team of Dataverse, is planning to [restructure the Dataverse UI as a single page application](#) (SPA). This was already announced a few years ago and developments have been slow so far, but for the coming year new developments are expected and the SPA has a prominent place on the [Dataverse roadmap](#).

Decoupling the different elements of the Portal, particularly the backend from the user interface, would allow for the user interface and the search to be customized towards ODISSEI's needs. Thus far, we did not invest in this as maintaining such elements ourselves is costly, but if Dataverse would provide elements that can be customized through their SPA developments, it would be valuable for the project to invest in this.

DANS is an active member of the Dataverse community and aims to contribute to new developments of the software where possible. In the past, DANS was able to contribute through projects including the ODISSEI roadmap project and SSHOC-NL which for instance supported the integration of the Croissant metadata standard into Dataverse.

Contributing to the SPA developments and showcasing the strength of this new restructuring of the software through the ODISSEI Portal is seen as a great opportunity in MacroScope. However, there is still some uncertainty about the planning on the side of Dataverse, and more information is needed to make the plans for MacroScope more concrete.

We envision that we will be able to provide a more detailed workplan and timeline for the developments in the second half of 2026 when the plans from the Dataverse consortium become clearer.

Innovating Search

Next to the interface that needs improvement, we also want to assess and improve the search functionality of the Portal. The most important feature of the Portal is its ability to make datasets discoverable for researchers.

Users have indicated that they are not always able to find the datasets they are looking for, which is something we would like to improve. An investigation of the Dataverse'

search functionalities, as well as of the possibilities of the knowledge graph (developed by VU) to improve or enrich the search results as well as assessing how researchers search for datasets, will help us identify blind-spots and areas for improvement in the Portal's search functionalities.

We also want to further investigate the possibilities for multilingual search. Many researchers do not speak Dutch and hence have difficulties finding datasets that are described in Dutch (such as the CBS microdata designs) in the Portal. Although we did realize enrichments of the metadata by attaching multilingual controlled vocabularies that allow finding datasets based on multilingual keywords, improving multilingual search further is an important challenge for the Portal.

While improving the search is an important challenge, this task will require more research and will start once we have more experience with the SPA from the interface developments described above and a better insight into the limitations of Dataverse search capabilities.

Connecting with other services in the Dutch SSH landscape

The Portal of course does not exist in isolation but is part of a larger infrastructure ODISSEI and CLARIAH are developing in SSHOC-NL and Macroscopic.

In our work on the Portal, we need to ensure that the Portal aligns and integrates with these other elements. Of course, the Portal needs to be connected to the data providers which provide metadata that is displayed in the Portal. This connection is already largely achieved and standardized, although small improvements have already been identified. The Portal should also align with the Data Access Broker, the data discovery Portals of CLARIAH (INEO) and the SSHOC-NL / Macroscopic Knowledge Graph. All these services are part of Macroscopic task 1.1, so a close collaboration is envisioned by design in the project proposal. Below we provide a brief outline of the work that has already been identified.

Data Access Broker

When a user has found a relevant dataset in the Portal, the user is redirected to the DAB where an access request procedure is initiated. The DAB is currently under development by SURF, and its initial focus is to provide a workflow for datasets available through the secure environment, SANE. The Portal already links to the DAB, and the Portal will provide relevant metadata to the DAB with respect to data access. Standardizing access conditions is an important task for both the DAB and the Portal team, which has already started to be addressed in work plans of SSHOC-NL.

INEO

As outlined in the [SSHOC deliverable](#) mentioned above, both ODISSEI and CLARIAH provide data discovery solutions for their community. That deliverable outlined

common challenges of both the ODISSEI Portal and CLARIAH's INEO such as data access (see above). The deliverable also identified areas for potential collaborations between DANS and HuC (who coordinates the development of INEO), such as FAIR assessments and enrichment of metadata.

Within Macroscopic and SSHOC-NL, the possibilities to align developments and address common challenges with respect to data discovery between ODISSEI and CLARIAH will be further explored. At the start of Macroscopic, task 1.1 plans to assess the services and components for data discovery that are already available at DANS and HuC (e.g., interface, search, harvesting etc.) to identify components that DANS and HuC could exchange and collaborate on.

Knowledge Graph

The Knowledge Graph plays a central role in the infrastructure that ODISSEI and CLARIAH want to provide. It should be able to link available resources, including data, tools, and research outputs to provide comprehensive information about the Macroscopic landscape. We aim to ensure that the Portal can supply the KG with detailed metadata from each of the Portal's datasets. We will monitor the further development of the KG as its scope and goals are being further defined to assess how the Portal and the KG can benefit from each other. It may, for instance, be possible that information available in the KG can be used to enrich the information in the Portal, improving data discovery.

In Summary

The ODISSEI Portal is one of the research infrastructure services available for the Dutch social sciences and humanities community. The Portal provides an entry point to find social sciences datasets available at various data providers in the Netherlands. In the Macroscopic project, the Portal will be further developed with the aim of maintaining a resilient and sustainable data discovery service. We plan to innovate the user interface and the search capabilities of the Portal. We envision the Portal to grow to include data from all ODISSEI members and allow more users to find the social sciences data they need. The Portal will be connected to European data portals and further embedded into the infrastructure developed in Macroscopic enabling the finding, accessing, and reusing of data and tools for the Dutch SSH community and beyond.